

Holotypes of longhorn beetles from the collection of Sergei V. Murzin (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)

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Abstract. Sixteen Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) holotypes from the collection of S. V. Murzin's (Moscow) were examined. Color photographs of all specimens are provided, including labels. Five holotypes described by Miroshnikov deposited in the collection were not discovered. Each name is followed by the original combination, reference to the original description, indication of the type locality, the current valid name of the taxon and texts of all specimens labels.

INTRODUCTION

Many Cerambycidae types are preserved in the collection of S. V. Murzin, Moscow. All his holotypes are listed here with corresponding labels and photographs. Holotypes of five species described by A. I. Miroshnikov, which were deposited (according to original descriptions) in Murzin's collection were not discovered (*Teledalpus zolotichini* Miroshnikov, 2000: 43 - "China, Shaanxi prov., Taibaishan nat. park 3000-3200 m," *Teledalpus lobanovi* Miroshnikov, 2021: 242 - "China, Sichuan Province, Maoxian County, SE Shangxinzhen Village, 2935 m a.s.l., 31°34'32"N / 103°47'33"E, 3.07.2012," *Teledalpus transitivus* Miroshnikov, 2021: 247 - "China, Yunnan Province, Deqen (Deqin) County, NE slope of SE Baima Mt. Ridge, SW of Benzilanzhen Village, 3225 m a.s.l., 28°10'44"N / 99°14'28"E, 5.06.2013," *Pachydissus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2018: 211 - "China, Yunnan Province, 54 km E of Tengchong, 2150 m, and *Dymasius murzini* Miroshnikov, 2017: 200 - "Sri Lanka, Kitugala, 600 m, 6°59'N / 80°24'E"). It is probable such specimens are still in Miroshnikov's collection.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

All information on the labels are in the original version.

RESULTS

Type Specimens of Longhorn Beetles in S. V. Murzin's collection

Teledalpus murzini Miroshnikov, 2000

Teledalpus murzini Miroshnikov, 2000a: 41.

Type locality: "China, North Sichuan, Nanping env., 3500 m".

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 1-2), male (length: 12.7 mm; width: 3.0 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "China, N Sichuan / env. Nanping, h=3500m / 10-19.06.1997 / leg. S Murzin"; 2) [red] "♂ HOLOTYPUS *Teleda- / palpus murzini* n. sp. / det. A. Miroshnikov / 2000".

Teledalpus zamotajlovi Miroshnikov, 2000

Teledalpus zamotajlovi Miroshnikov, 2000a: 41.

Type locality: "China, N Sichuan, Juizhaigou, 4000 m".

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 3-4), male (length: 14.0 mm; width: 3.3 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "China, N Sichuan / Juizhaigou, h=4000m / 21-23.06.1997 / leg. S Murzin"; 2) [red] "♂ HOLOTYPUS *Teleda- / palpus zamotajlovi* / det. A. Miroshnikov / 2000 n. sp."

Neorhamnusium melanocephalum Miroshnikov & Lin, 2015

Neorhamnusium melanocephalum Miroshnikov & Lin, 2015: 294.

Type locality: "China, Yunnan Prov., Laojunshan, river above Shangliju, 2755 m, 26°45'20"N / 99°37'16"E".

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 5-6), female (length: 20.5 mm; width: 5.9 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "China, Yunnan Prov., / Laojunshan, river above / Shangliju, 2755 m, 26°45'20"N / 99°37'16"E, 25.VI.2014, / leg. I. Belousov & I. Kabak"; 2) [red] "HOLOTYPUS ♀ / *Neorhamnusium melanocephalum* sp. n. / det. A. Miroshnikov et / M.-Y. Lin 2015".

Katarinia murzini Miroshnikov, 2015

Katarinia murzini Miroshnikov, 2015: 287.

Type locality: "China, Shaanxi Prov., Zhouzhi env., Taibaishan nat. park, 1350 m, 34°01'N / 108°06'E".

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 7-8), male (length: 10.2 mm; width: 2.8 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "CHINA, Shaanxi prov., / env. Zhouzhi, Taibaishan / nat. park, h=1350 m / 30.V.1999. M. Murzin lg."; 2) [red] "HOLOTYPUS ♂ / *Katarinia murzini* sp. n. / det. A. Miroshnikov 2015".

***Katarinia belousovi* Miroshnikov, 2015**

Katarinia belousovi Miroshnikov, 2015: 289.

Type locality: “China, Yunnan Prov., Zhongdian env., 3800-4100 m”.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 9-10), male (length: 11.7 mm; width: 3.4 mm), “CHINA N., Yunnan pr., WNW Zhongdian, 3800-4100m, 13.VII.2007 / I. Belousov, I. Kabak leg.”; 2) [red] “HOLOTYPUS ♂ / *Katarinia belousovi* sp. n. / det. A. Miroshnikov 2015”.

***Anoplodera* (s. str.) *sergeii* Miroshnikov, 2000**

Anoplodera (s. str.) *sergeii* Miroshnikov, 2000b: 82.

Type locality: “China, North Sichuan, Songpan”.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 11-12), male (length: 7.9 mm; width: 2.3 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “China, N Sichuan, / Songpan, / 9.07.1997 / leg. S Murzin”; 2) [red] “♂ HOLOTYPUS *Anop- / lodera* (s. str.) *sergeii* / det. A. Miroshnikov / 1999 n. sp.”.

***Anoplodera* (s. str.) *shamaevi* Miroshnikov, 2000**

Anoplodera (s. str.) *shamaevi* Miroshnikov, 2000b: 82.

Type locality: “China, Qinghai, 70 km S.Xining, Garang, 3600 m”.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 13-14), female (length: 10.3 mm; width: 2.9 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “China, Qinghai / 70 km S.Xining, / Garang, h=3600m / 25.VI.[19]97 A. Shamaev lg.”; 2) [red] “♀ HOLOTYPUS *Anop- / lodera* (s. str.) *shamaevi* / det. A. Miroshnikov / 1999 n. sp.”.

***Pygostrangalia gialaii* (Murzin, 1988)**

Strangalia (*Pygostrangalia*) *gialaii* Murzin, 1988: 163.

Type locality: Vietnam, Gia Lai province, Buon Loi, 40 km N Ankkhe.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 15-16), female (length: 13.2 mm; width: 2.6 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “SRV Prov. Gialai- / Contum, Buon-Loi, / 40 km N Ankkhe / VI.1980”; 2) [red] “Holotypus / *Strangalia* (*Pygostrangalia*) / *gialaii* sp. n. / S. Murzin”.

***Pygostrangalia medvedevi* (Murzin, 1988)**

Strangalia (*Pygostrangalia*) *medvedevi* Murzin, 1988: 164.

Type locality: Vietnam, Vinh-Phu Province, Tam Dao, 900 m. [in Russian]

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 17-18), female (length: 8.9 mm; width: 1.9 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “Vietnam / Tam Dao / 26.V.1985 / L. Medvedev” [in Russian]; 2) [red] “Holotypus / *Strangalia* (*Pygostrangalia*) / *medvedevi* sp. n. / S. Murzin”.

***Gnathostrangalia bilineatithorax* (Pic, 1922)**

Strangalia (s. str.) *tonkinea* Murzin, 1988: 162 (according to *Pygostrangalia bilineatithorax* Holzschuh, 1991: 24).

Type locality: Vietnam, Vinh-Phu Province, Tam Dao, 900 m. [in Russian].

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 19-20), male (length: 20.0 mm; width: 4.6 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “Vietnam / Tam Dao / 26.V.1985 / L. Medvedev” [in Russian]; 2) [red] “Holotypus / *Strangalia* (s. str.) / *tonkinea* sp. n. / S. Murzin”.

***Trypogeus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2014**

Trypogeus murzini Miroshnikov, 2014a: 57.

Type locality: “S Cambodia, Phnom Bokor National Park, 600 m”.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 21-23), male (length: 9.5 mm; width: 3.1 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “CAMBODIA / Phnom Bokor Nat. Park / 600 m, 24-28.XI.2007 / S. Murzin leg.”; 2) [red] “HOLOTYPUS ♂ / *Trypogeus murzini* / sp. n. det. / A. Miroshnikov 2013”.

***Stenhomalus* (s. str.) *murzini* Miroshnikov, 1989**

Stenhomalus murzini Miroshnikov, 1989: 107.

Type locality: W. Africa, PRR Guinea, Kindia, Pastoria.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 24-25), male (length: 5.1 mm; width: 1.2 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “W. AFRICA, PRR GUINEA / KINDIA, PASTORIA / 31 V 1983 S.V. MURZIN / PRK-4 UF” [in Russian]; 2) [red] “Holotypus 1987 / *Stenhomalus* ♂ / *murzini* m. / det. A. Miroshnikov”.

***Tetraommatus unifasciatus* Murzin, 1988**

Tetraommatus unifasciatus Murzin, 1988: 165.

Type locality: Vietnam, Gia Lai province, 5 km N Ankkhe.

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 26-27), female (length: 6.7 mm; width: 1.4 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “Vietnam / 5 km N Ankkhe / 19.X.1979 / L. Medvedev”; 2) [red] “Holotypus / *Tetraommatus* / *unifasciatus* sp. n. / S. Murzin”.

***Paraclytus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2014**

Paraclytus murzini Miroshnikov, 2014b: 82.

Type locality: “China: Sichuan Province, Liangshan Mts, S Xichang, 3000 m”

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 28-29), female (length: 13.2 mm; width: 3.5 mm) with 2 labels: 1) “CHINA S. SICHUAN / Liangshan Mts. S.Xichang / h=3000m, 1.VII.2002 / leg. S.Murzin, I.Shokhin”; 2) [red] “HOLOTYPUS ♀ / *Paraclytus murzini* / sp. n. det. / A. Miroshnikov 2013”.

Figs. 1-6. *Teledalpus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2000: 1- Holotype, male; 2- Labels of the holotype; *Teledalpus zamotajlovi* Miroshnikov, 2000: 3- Holotype, male; 4- Labels of the holotype; *Neorhamnusium melanocephalum* Miroshnikov & Lin, 2015: 5- Holotype, female; 6- Labels of the holotype.

7

CHINA, Shaanxi prov.,
 env. Zhouzhi, Taibaishan
 nat. park, h=1350 m
 30.V.1999. M. Murzin lg.

HOLOTYPE ♂
Katarinia murzini sp. n.
 det. A. Miroshnikov 2015

8

9

CHINA, N. Yunnan pr.
 WNW Zhongdian
 3800-4100m, 13.VII.2007
 I. Belousov, I. Kabak leg.

HOLOTYPE ♂
Katarinia belousovi sp. n.
 det. A. Miroshnikov 2015

10

11

China, N Sichuan, prov.
 Songpan,
 h = 3600 - 4000m
 02.IV - 9.07. 1997.
 leg. S. Murzin

HOLOTYPE Anop-
lodera (s. str.) sergeii
 det. A. Miroshnikov
 1999 n.sp.

12

CHINA, Qinghai
 70 km S.Xining,
 Garang, h=3600m
 25.VI.97 A. Shamaev lg.

HOLOTYPE Anop-
lodera (s. str.) shamaevi
 det. A. Miroshnikov
 1999 n.sp.

14

13

Figs. 7-14. *Katarinia murzini* Miroshnikov, 2015: 7- Holotype, male; 8- Labels of the holotype; *Katarinia belousovi* Miroshnikov, 2015: 9- Holotype, male; 10- Labels of the holotype; *Anoplodera (s. str.) sergeii* Miroshnikov, 2000: 11- Holotype, male; 12- Labels of the holotype; *Anoplodera (s. str.) shamaevi* Miroshnikov, 2000: 13- Holotype, female; 14- Labels of the holotype.

Figs. 15-20. *Strangalia (Pygostrangalia) gialai* Murzin, 1988: 15- Holotype, female; 16- Labels of the holotype; *Strangalia (Pygostrangalia) medvedevi* Murzin, 1988: 17- Holotype, female; 18- Labels of the holotype; *Strangalia (s. str.) tonkinea* Murzin, 1988: 19- Holotype, male; 20- Labels of the holotype.

Figs. 21-27. *Trypogeus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2014: 21- Holotype, male; 22- Genitals of the holotype; 23- Labels of the holotype; *Stenhomalus murzini* Miroshnikov, 1989: 24- Holotype, male; 25- Labels of the holotype; *Tetraommatus unifasciatus* Murzin, 1988: 26- Holotype, female; 27- Labels of the holotype.

Figs. 28-34. *Paraclytus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2014: 28- Holotype, female; 29- Labels of the holotype; *Arachnoparmena zaitzevi* Murzin, 1988: 30- Holotype, male; 31- Side view of holotype; 32- Labels of the holotype; *Microlenecamptus sexmaculatus* Murzin, 1988: 33- Holotype, female; 34- Labels of the holotype.

Arachnoparmena zaitzevi Murzin, 1988

Arachnoparmena zaitzevi Murzin, 1988: 167.

Type locality: Vietnam, Vinh-Phu Province, Tam Dao, 900 m. [in Russian].

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 30-33), male (length: 3.8 mm; width: 1.6 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "Vietnam / Tam Dao / 19.IV.1986 / Yu. Zaytsev" [in Russian]; 2) [red] "Holotypus / *Arachnoparmena* / *zaitzevi* g. sp. n. S. Murzin".

Microlenecamptus sexmaculatus Murzin, 1988

Microlenecamptus sexmaculatus Murzin, 1988: 167.

Type locality: Vietnam, Vinh-Phu Province, Tam Dao, 900 m. [in Russian].

Type material. Holotype (Figs. 33-34), female (length: 13.5 mm; width: 3.5 mm) with 2 labels: 1) "Vietnam / Vinh-Phu Prov. / Tam Dao / 5.VI.1981 / Yu. Zaytsev" [in Russian]; 2) [red] "Holotypus / *Microlenecamptus* / *sexmaculatus* sp. n. / S. Murzin".

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